

Research Article

WasteWell: The Food Waste Management App

Fatin Nur Aida Ismail ¹, Anis Shazwani Sohaizad ², and Azyanee Luqman ^{3,*}

¹ Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; fatinaida.ismail@gmail.com; 0009-0008-8732-3967

² Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; shazwanisohaizad@gmail.com; 0009-0009-4914-309X

³ Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; azyanee@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-1351-468X

* Correspondence: azyanee@uitm.edu.my; +60129590120.

Abstract: *Undoubtedly, food waste in restaurant industry is not properly managed. Furthermore, restaurant owners do not know how to manage their food waste and they are not aware of the nearest compost facility available. Thus, WasteWell is proposed as the mobile application to match and connect restaurant owners with the nearest compost facility through location based. It is the first of its kind app that focuses on food waste management. WasteWell is a unique platform that assists restaurant owners in managing food waste by connecting them with the nearest compost facility. This business idea would ensure a balance between economic growth and environmental care by providing side income to the restaurant owners whilst reducing waste sent to landfills as well air and land pollution.*

Keywords: mobile application; food waste management; restaurant industry.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888407

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

The WasteWell application serves as a vital solution to the global challenge of improper food waste disposal within the restaurant industry. The application's significance is magnified by the recognition that food waste's disposal in landfills gives rise to a notable methane output, a potent greenhouse gas with heightened climate change implications compared to carbon dioxide. Furthermore, the app addresses the knowledge gap among restaurant owners regarding accessible composting sites, a factor hindering sustainable waste management. By offering a comprehensive approach, the WasteWell application not only promotes responsible waste disposal but also contributes to reducing environmental contamination and fostering a more sustainable future for the restaurant industry. It is the first app of its kind to concentrate on food waste management and connect restaurant owners to the closest compost facility. The development of the app is motivated by a shared objective to create a mobile application that facilitates the connection between restaurant owners and the closest composting facility, thereby aiding them in the proper disposal of food waste.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The problem is that restaurant owners do not know how to manage their food waste and are unaware of the nearest available compost facility. The method used to approach this problem is by developing an app in order to assist restaurant owners in managing their food waste. The app would connect restaurant owners with the nearest compost facility. Apart from generating side income for the

restaurant owners, this effort would help to reduce waste sent to landfills as well as air and land pollution. Such an app has the potential to create a positive impact on restaurant waste and help in the process of reducing it.

The users of this app would be the restaurant owners, compost facility providers and local municipal councils. The key metrics of the app would encompass number of deals between restaurant owners and compost facilities as well as satisfactory reviews by the users. On top of that, revenue streams would come from the transaction fees involved.

Figure 1. WasteWell app.

3. FINDINGS

Our discovery highlights the revolutionary influence of WasteWell in addressing food waste in restaurants. The initiative helps restaurants to reduce food waste by easily connecting them to nearby composting facilities. This direct link allows restaurants to compost their organic waste instead of landfills, lowering pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. The software simplifies appropriate waste disposal by connecting to this connection, addressing environmental and economic problems. The WasteWell app reduces food waste and promotes sustainable waste management for restaurants, communities, and the earth through this creative approach.

The WasteWell app helps restaurant owners generate cash from food waste, which has significant economic growth implications. Restaurants may boost their profits by turning waste into a resource. This method minimizes garbage disposal expenses and is sustainable. The income promotes circular economy ideas, community engagement, and responsible consumption, benefiting businesses and local economies. WasteWell app can boost local sustainability by partnering with local businesses (Staff, 2022). This shows how innovative solutions like WasteWell may boost economic growth and sustainability whilst helping individual businesses.

4. DISCUSSION

This business idea would ensure a balance between economic growth and environmental care by providing side income to the restaurant owners whilst reducing waste sent to the air and landfill. The waste from the restaurants would be used to create compost, which in turn would be used as a natural fertilizer. This would reduce the need for chemical-based fertilizers, which can be damaging to the environment. This idea could create a greater balance between the economy and the environment.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the WasteWell application stands as a transformative solution to the pervasive challenge of improper food waste disposal in the restaurant industry. By connecting restaurant owners with nearby composting facilities, it not only addresses a pressing concern but also mitigates environmental hazards and contributes to a more sustainable future. This innovative approach exemplifies how technology can foster responsible waste disposal, reduce pollution, and promote economic growth. The app's potential to generate income for restaurant owners while curbing waste underscores its role in advancing the circular economy and local sustainability. By bridging the gap between economic prosperity and environmental well-being, WasteWell showcases the power of innovative solutions in shaping a brighter future for businesses, communities, and the planet.

Acknowledgments: WasteWell has received a silver award in The National 3-Minute Business Idea Pitch and Innovation Competition (3-MPiC) 2023 organized by Faculty of Business and Management, UiTM Cawangan Kelantan, Malaysia.

References

Staff, S. (2022, December 9). Reasons Why Recycling is a Profitable Side Hustle. Stop Having a Boring Life - If Life Is Boring, You're Doing It Wrong! Retrieved from <https://stophavingaboringlife.com/reasons-why-recycling-is-a-profitable-side-hustle/>